
PhET SIMULATION AND GENDER ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN PHYSICS

By

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Abstract

This study was carried out to examine the effect of PhET Simulation technology and gender on secondary school Physics students' academic performance in Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. Three research questions were raised and three research hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted Quasi-experimental design using non-randomized pre-test post-test control group. The population consisted of all the 3,183 senior secondary one Physics students during 2023/2024 academic session in all the 15 public secondary schools in Uyo L.G.A., Akwa Ibom State. A sample size of 202 respondents was selected using Purposive sampling technique. One experimental and one control groups were drawn giving a total of two intact classes. The experimental group was taught using PhET Simulation technology while the control group was taught using expository method. A researcher-made instrument titled 'Physics Performance Test (PPT) was used as pre-test and post-test. The instrument was face validated by three validators in Faculty of Education, University of Uyo and a reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained using Test-retest method. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer all the research questions and Analysis of Covariance was used to test all the hypotheses at .05 significant level. The findings of the study showed a significant difference in the academic performance of Physics students taught with PhET Simulation technology and those taught using expository method. The finding showed a no significant difference in the performance of male and female Physics students taught with PhET Simulation technology and a no significant difference also exists in the academic performance of urban and rural Physics students taught with PhET Simulation technology. Based on these findings, it was concluded that PhET Simulation technology enhances students' academic performance in Physics in Uyo LGA, Akwa Ibom State. It is recommended among others that PhET Simulation technology should be used in the teaching-learning process to enhance students' performance in Physics.

Keywords: *PhET Simulation technology, gender, secondary school, Physics, students' academic performance.*

Introduction

Science is an integral part of human society and its impact is felt in every sphere of human life, so much that it is intricately linked with a nation's development. The relevance of science to national goals, aspirations and economy dictates to a large extent the huge commitment, contributions and support which nations make towards science and technological advancement. Science is the bedrock on which modern day technological breakthrough depends on (Cakici and Yvuz, 2016). Science as a branch of knowledge is the systematic study of things around us. The totality of knowledge obtained from such studies constitutes scientific knowledge. Science is a field of study that is basically concerned with the understanding of the physical world. This understanding enables scientists to uncover the nature of things, events, technological development and events to harness such things and events for the benefits of mankind (Onyeneke, 2021).

Physics is a branch of science that deals with the study matter and energy and the relationship that exist between them. Physics examines the relationship between matter and the underlying forces of nature. It involves the study of laws, principles and concepts that converge all the components of the universe and appreciates their state of orderliness (Hake, 2020). Physics is an aspect of science that deal with the structure of matter and interaction between the fundamental constituents of the observable universe. It is one of the most fundamental scientific disciplines upon which other science subjects depend on, since its main goal is to understand how the universe behave as well as how the existing matter interact with the universe (Ang, Afzal and Crawford, 2021).

PhET, an open-source program, is a product of the University of Colorado. Programmers designed these simulations to make initial interactions straightforward and intuitive, resulting in immediate, useful feedback for sense-making. The selection of interactive features focuses on concepts, and the simulation's intuitive layout ensures that students quickly understand how to interact with it (Makransky *et al.*, 2019). Students derive benefits from PhET simulations by having the opportunity to virtually experience fundamental physics concepts without having to purchase expensive real-life equipment. It has the potential to be effective in teaching science lessons in high school and college (Fabian, 2020). The simulations have been developed so that students can investigate physical laws such as Ohm's law. Through visualization, demonstrations, and illustrations, PhET interactive simulation gives an alternative method to the expository method and can boost students' learning (Fabian, 2020)

One technology resource commonly used in physics classes is Physics Education Technology (PhET) interactive simulations because it has many features. PhET simulations are considered one of the best education software because they can be accessed for free online or downloaded and saved as web pages, jar files, or PDF files that can run on a flash player). PhET simulations are research-based, highly interactive, animated, and easy to use. They create a game-like environment, can be used to model real-life scenarios, and do not need many computer specifications (PhET, 2021). PhET interactive simulation activities offer more to the way students learn physics in a way that intrigues the mind of learners with mouth-watering visualizations of abstract physics concepts; hence, they develop a deeper understanding of physics concepts (Ganasen and Shamuganathan, 2017; Perkins, 2020). These features and advantages make PhET simulations ideal for physics in Nigerian schools as they can be easily incorporated into mainstream learning. In line with this, Buday *et al.*, (2023) posited that PhET simulation is valid for improving the performance of the students in Physics. Kozielska and Kedzierski (2020) opined that PhET simulations are virtual replications of instructional scenarios that offer students the opportunity to learn about

phenomena in conditions where it is tough to carry out due to time challenges, safety concerns, or absence of adequate instruments and thus extending the space between the physical and theoretical concepts (Tien and Hamid, 2020). PhET simulations mimic real-world phenomena through animations, visualizations, and interactive elements, making abstract concepts more tangible. Essentially, they act as dynamic models, simplifying complex systems and offering a richer learning experience than traditional methods (Banda and Nzabahimana, 2021).

According to Tien and Hamid (2020), teaching that trigger active learning is more of students-centered and modern strategies of teaching that involves the use of simulations. The use of teaching technologies that enable active learning which improves teachers' self-efficacy as well as the quality of teaching and learning. Educators have long supported an innovative transformation in education where teaching and learning practices are based on the integration of technology to accommodate the needs of different and diverse students with the changing trends and the emerging patterns of global education that facilitate lifelong learning (Fisher, LaFerriere and Rixon 2020). Today's learning environment has changed a lot which leads to the importance of self-directed learning among students and at the same time opens up opportunities for instructors to improve students' learning experiences regardless of whether the learning takes place in the classroom or online (Ang *et al.*, 2021).

The method adopted for teaching any concept in physics has a great role to play on the learning and comprehensive ability of every student and this will positively affect their performance in both internal and external examinations (Ema and Etim, 2017). Academic performance is the measurement of students' learning progress across various academic subjects, this could be measured through test, examination, and classroom participation. Teachers and educators typically measure academic success and achievement using classroom performance, results of standardized tests and graduation rates. Students' academic performance tends to show the efficacy or otherwise of schools and tends to determine the future of students. According to Fabian (2020), academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks given by a teacher and or educational goals set by students and teacher to be achieved over a period of time. Improving students' academic performance in Physics in particular calls for implementation of innovative strategies to make lessons more interesting and meaningful. The landscape of education is undergoing a significant transformation, driven by the rapid evolution of innovative technologies.

Researches from Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) showed a significant difference in students' performance based on gender. Apart of gender, school location is another known factor that affects students' performance. School location refers to the particular place, in relation to other areas in the physical environment (rural or urban), where the school is sited. School location is the place where the school situates. The environments in which a student finds his/herself has been considered by scholars to exert great influence on students towards learning (Sowunmi, 2017). School location plays a significant role on students' academic performance irrespective of gender. School location in this context refers to the environment "urban and rural" where the school is located. Researches from Akpomudjere (2020), Ikechukwu (2021) and Ekpenyong (2017) showed a no significant difference in students' performance based on school location. While research from Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) showed a significant difference in students' performance based on school location. It is against this background that this study sought to compare the effect of PhET simulation and expository method on Senior Secondary one (SS I) students' academic performance in Physics in Uyo Local Government Area.

Statement of Problem

Effective teaching of Physics is the backbone of Engineering and science subject, as it laid the foundation for technological and scientific advancement. Besides, for a Physics student to be successful, the student needs to properly learn physics concepts in the practical aspects as much as theoretical aspects (Godwin *et al.*, 2015). If this is the case, there is an urgent need to tackle the present precarious situation regarding the decline in Physics students' academic performance in West African Certificate Examination (Akani, 2015). The WAEC Chief Examiners Report of 2022, 2023 and 2024 averred that several factors were attributed to the students' poor achievement in Physics, one of such is the tediousness of conventional and teacher-centered strategy to teach Physics, as this strategy makes physics concepts abstract and more difficult for student comprehension (Taneo and Moleño, 2022). This challenge calls for the use of student-centered strategy that will help students understand physics concepts as they prepared for West African Senior secondary School Certificate Examination to improve their performance in Physics as well as acquire practical skills. Hence, this study investigated the effects of PhET Simulation and Gender on Physics students' academic performance in Uyo Local Government Area.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to determine the effect of PhET Simulation on academic Performance of Physics students' in Uyo Local Government Area. Specifically, this study sought to:

1. determine the difference in academic performances of Physics students taught with PhET Simulation and those taught using Expository method.
2. find out the difference in academic performances of male and female Physics students taught using PhET Simulation.
3. examine the difference in academic performances of urban and rural Physics students taught using PhET Simulation.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised:

- i. What is the difference in academic performances of students taught Physics with PhET Simulation and those taught with Expository method?
- ii. What is the difference in academic performances of male and female students' taught Physics using PhET Simulation?
- iii. What is the difference in academic performances of urban and rural students' taught Physics using PhET Simulation?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance.

- Ho₁ There is no significant difference in the academic performances of students taught Physics with PhET Simulation and those taught using Expository method.
- Ho₂ There is no significant difference in the academic performances of male and female students' taught Physics using PhET Simulation.
- Ho₃ There is no significant difference in the academic performances of urban and rural students taught Physics using PhET Simulation?

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design, specifically the non-randomized pre-test post- test design with two intact classes. The area of this study was Uyo Local Government

Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The area is bounded in the North by Uruan L.G.A, in the South by Ibesikpo Asutan L.G.A., in the East by Itu L.G.A. and in the West by Abak Local Government; the area has 15 public secondary schools classified under urban and rural. The population of study consisted of all the 3,183 SSI Physics students in the 15 public secondary schools for 2023/2024 session in Uyo Local Government Area. The sample size for this study consisted of 202 Senior Secondary two students drawn from 15 public secondary schools in the area using purposive sampling techniques under the underlisted criteria:

- a. Schools that usually present candidates for the Senior Secondary Certificate Examination (SSCE).
- b. Schools that are coeducational.
- c. Schools that have computer laboratory with at least 30 functional computers with internet connectivity.
- d. Schools that have Physics teachers with at least three years teaching experience.

The researcher-made instrument titled: Physics Performance Test (PPT) was used for data collection. The Physics Performance Test (PPT) was developed on the concept of Motion for pretest and post-test. A total of 50 multiple-choice items were constructed. The content validity of PPT was established via the expert opinions of three science educators: including high school physics teachers, inspectors, and professors. In order to establish the reliability of the instrument; the Physics Performance Test (PPT) was administered to 30 physics students who were not part of the main study but equivalent in all aspects to the students in the main study using the test-retest method. The scores obtained from these respondents were analyzed using the Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.83. The instrument was therefore considered to be highly reliable and useful in collecting the required data for the study.

Experimental Procedure

A recommendation letter was obtained from the Head of Department of Science Education, University of Uyo to the principals of the selected schools in Uyo, for permission to use the secondary schools for the study. Permission was obtained from the principals of the selected schools to use qualified Physics teachers and Physics students in Senior Secondary one (SSI) classes. Two Senior Secondary one (SSI) Physics teachers in all the selected schools formed the research assistants (one in the urban and one in the rural) who were briefed by the researcher for a period of one week on how to use PhET simulation strategy. The experimental and control groups were taught the concept of "Motion" the same day by the research assistants. The entire procedure lasted for five weeks:

Stage 1: Week one was used by the researcher to visit the sampled schools to solicit for the Principals approval to use the school for the study.

Stage 2: Week two was used by the researcher to brief the research assistants on what PhET Simulation is all about.

Stage 3: Week three was used to pretest all the experimental and control groups.

Stage 4: Week four was used to teach the experimental and control groups using PhET simulation and Expository strategy respectively. After the treatment, posttest will be administered to both experimental and control groups.

Stage 5: Data collection and analysis took place fifth week of the study.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Data were collected by administering the Physics Performance Test (PPT) on Motion as pretest to the students before the treatment. After treatment, PPT was administered as post-test to the students immediately the instrument were collected, marked, scored and were used for analysis; mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. ANCOVA was used since the pretest and posttest scores was used to test the difference between two groups when having pairs of scores (pretest and posttest). The choice of ANCOVA was informed by the use of pretest as covariate to control for the effects of use of non-equivalent groups.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the difference in the academic performances of students taught Physics with PhET Simulation and those taught with Expository method?

Table 4.1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Pre-test and Post-test Scores of Students Performance in Physics taught using PhET Simulation and those taught using expository method.

Treatment Mean Groups	n	Pre-test		Post-test	
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD
Gain PhET Simulation (Experimental)	100	22.11	3.64	67.25	7.19
45.14 Expository (Control)	102	22.83	4.16	60.02	9.00
37.19 Total	202				

The result in Table 4.1 reveals the pre-test and post-test mean scores of experimental students taught Physics with PhET simulation technology of 22.11 and 67.25 with their respective standard deviations of 3.64 and 7.19. The result further shows the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students taught using expository method of 22.83 and 60.02 and their respective standard deviations of 4.16 and 9.00 respectively. This shows that there was a higher performance in the post-test scores of the two groups but the experimental group has the highest mean gain score of 45.14 against 37.19 of the expository group. This means that utilization of PhET simulation technology in teaching Physics concepts enhanced students' performance than the expository method.

Research Question 2

What is the difference in the academic performances of male and female students' taught Physics using PhET Simulation?

Table 4.2 Mean and Standard Deviation of SS II Male and Female Students' taught Physics with PhET technology

PhET Simulation Gender	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean		Gain
	n	\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD		
Male 41.19	50	20.60	3.99	61.79	7.91		
Female 41.36	50	20.00	4.40	61.36	7.58		
Total	100						

The result in Table 4.2 revealed the pre-test and post-test mean scores of male students taught Physics with PhET simulation technology of 20.60 and 61.79 with their respective standard deviations of 3.99 and 7.91. The result further shows the pre-test and post-test mean scores of female students taught with PhET simulation technology of 20.00 and 61.36 with their respective standard deviations of 4.40 and 7.58 respectively. This shows that there was equal performance in the post-test scores of male and female students with a slightly higher mean score in favour of male students, though not significant. This means that both male and female students performed equally when taught Physics using PhET simulation technology.

Research Question 3

What is the difference in the academic performances of urban and rural students' taught Physics using PhET simulation Technology?

Table 4.3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Urban and Rural Students taught Physics with PhET simulation technology

School Location	n	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain
		\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Urban	50	22.12	3.23	62.82	7.89	40.7
Rural	50	22.10	4.05	62.68	6.47	40.58
Total	100					

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the academic performances of students taught Physics with PhET Simulation Technology and those taught using Expository method.

Table 4.4: Summary of ANCOVA analysis of SS I Students’ taught Physics with PhET simulation technology and those taught with expository method (n=202).

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	
Decision						
Corrected Model	495.534	2	247.767	3.692	.027	
Intercept	21589.003	1	21589.003	321.672	.001	
Pre-test	108.783	1	108.783	1.621	.204	
Instructional methods* Pretest	327.343	1	327.343	49.877	.001	Sig.
Error	13355.872	199	67.115			
Total	780944.000	202				
Corrected Total	13851.406	201				

The result of ANCOVA analysis in Table 4.4 reveals that {F-ratio (2,202) is 49.877, $p=.001 < 0.05$ }. The implication of this, is that the significant value (.001) was found to be less than the alpha value (0.05) in which the decision was based. With this result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the performance of SS I students in Physics taught the concept of Motion, Force and Friction with PhET simulation technology and those taught with expository method was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the performance of SS I students in Physics taught with PhET Simulation technology and those taught with expository method. The result points to the fact the experimental group taught with PhET technology had a significant performance over the control group which was the expository group.

4.1.5 Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in the academic performances of male and female students’ taught Physics using PhETSimulation.

Table 4.5: Summary of ANCOVA analysis of SS I male and female students taught Physics with PhET Simulation technology (n=100).

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	
Decision						
Corrected Model	511.015	2	255.507	3.429	.036	
Intercept	9941.562	1	9941.562	133.433	.001	
Pre-test	358.855	1	358.855	4.816	.031	
Gender*Pretest N/Sig.*	183.876	1	183.876	2.468	.119	
Error	7227.095	97	74.506			
Total	371709.000	100				
Corrected Total	7738.110	99				

The result of the ANCOVA analysis in Table 4.5 reveals that {F-ratio (2, 100) = 2.468, $p=.119 > 0.05$ }. The implication of this is that the significant value (.119) was found to be greater than the alpha value (0.05) which the decision was based. With this result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the performance of SS I male and female students in Physics taught the concept of Motion, Force and Friction with PhET Simulation was

upheld. This implies that there is no significant difference in the performance of SS I male and female students in Physics taught with PhET Simulation. This means that the difference in performance between male and female students when taught Physics using PhET Simulation was not significant.

4.1.6 Research Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the academic performances of urban and rural students taught Physics using PhET Simulation?

Table 4.6: Summary of ANCOVA analysis of SS I urban and rural students taught Physics with PhET Simulation(n=100).

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-ratio	P-value
Decision					
Corrected Model	46.485	2	23.242	.444	.643
Intercept	11558.328	1	11558.328	220.602	.001
Pre-test	26.595	1	26.595	.508	.478
School_location*	21.418	1	21.418	.409	.524
N/Sig.*					
Pretest					
Error	5082.265	97	52.394		
Total	405185.000	100			
Corrected Total	5128.750	99			

The result of the ANCOVA analysis in Table 4.6 reveals that $\{F(2,100) = .409, p = .524 > 0.05\}$. The implication of this is that the significant value (.524) was found to be greater than the alpha value (0.05) which the decision was based. With this result, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the performance of SS I urban and rural students in Physics taught the concept of Motion, Force and Friction with PhET technology was upheld. This implies that there is no significant difference in the performance of SS I urban and rural students in Physics taught with PhET technology. This result points to the fact that urban and rural students taught with PhET technology performed equally.

Discussion of Findings

Effect of PhET Simulation Technology and Expository method on Academic Performance of Students in Physics

The result of hypothesis one revealed that academic performance of Physics students significantly differs when taught using PhET technology and expository method. This means that students taught with PhET simulation technology performed higher than those taught with expository method. The reason for this result could be due to the fact that students had opportunities of interacting with the lesson contents, classmates and teachers without limitations, and this eventually enhances their learning and performance. Students who were typically shy in class were free to interact and ask questions for clarifications using PhET simulation technology.

This finding is in line with the position of Cezar *et al.*, (2024), who posited that computer simulations can be a valuable tool for enhancing both learning outcomes and

student motivation in Physics education. The outcome of this study is in agreement with the findings of Jebuni-Adanu *et al.*, (2023) who revealed that PhET simulation is valid for improving the performance of the students on Ohm's Law. The finding of this study also agrees with the findings of Banda and Nzabahimana (2023) who revealed that PhET simulation-based learning improved the learning of oscillations and waves. The reason for this result could be to the fact that PhET simulation-based learning provides visualizations and teaching aids that help easily understand content knowledge, hence improving students' academic performance.

Effect of PhET Simulation on Academic Performance of Students in Physics based on Gender

The findings of hypothesis two revealed that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of SS I male and female Physics students taught with PhET technology. This means that male and female students taught Physics concept using PhET technology performed equally. This finding is possible in view of the fact that when both male and female students are exposed to the same instructional strategy, they are likely going to learn at the same pace and thus, there might not be any significant difference in their academic performance. The finding of this study is in tandem with that of Joel and Ephraim (2019) whose finding showed a no statistically significant difference in the achievements of male and female students taught using CAI. The finding of this study lends credence to that of Attah and Ita (2017) whose finding showed that gender has no significant influence on academic performance of students. The finding of this study contradicts that of Nnamani and Oyibe (2016) whose finding revealed a significant difference in the mean achievement of secondary school students based on gender.

Effect of PhET Technology on Academic Performance of Students in Physics based on School Location

The result of hypothesis three revealed that there is no significant difference in the academic performance of SS I urban and rural Physics students taught the concept of Motion, Force and Friction with PhET technology. This means that urban and rural students taught using PhET technology performed equally. This finding could be attributed to the fact that when both urban and rural students are exposed to the same instructional strategies, they might as well learn at the same pace. The finding of this study lends credence to that of Akpomudjere (2020) whose finding showed that school location does not have significant effects on student's performance. The finding is in line with that of Ikechuku-Abamba (2021) whose finding showed that there is no significant difference between rural and urban students' achievement in Physics. The finding is also in line with that of Ekpenyong (2017) whose finding showed that school location has no significant influence on students' academic performance in Social studies. The finding contradict that of Afolabi and Elegbede (2022) whose finding showed a significant difference in the academic performance of students' in secondary schools based on school location.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the study concluded that utilization of PHET simulation technology in teaching Physics concepts enhanced students' performance than the expository method of teaching.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion drawn, the following recommendations are made to improve students' performance in Physics:

- (i) Physics teachers should utilize and encourage students on the use of PhET simulation Technology as it promotes flexible, autonomous and independent learning.
- (ii) Physics teachers should motivate boys and girls to learn effectively to avoid gender disparities in performance.

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